

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of some 5-Arylazo-3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones

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Introduction of azo group in several types of compounds has been found to considerably enhance their antibacterial activity. It was felt desirable therefore to study the effect of the introduction of azo group in the 3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones on their fungicidal activity. With this aim in view the 5-arylazo derivatives of several 3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones were prepared earlier by the present author (this *Journal*, 1958, **35**, 576) and Bhargava, Pantulu, and Rao (*ibid.*, 1957, **34**, 475). The present communication is in continuation of the earlier work. The results are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound.	Colour.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
5-Ph. azo-3- <i>m</i> -chloroPh- 2- <i>m</i> -chloroPh-IT	Greyish brown	65%	135-37°	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ON ₄ Cl ₂ S	12.73	12.69
5-Ph. azo-3- <i>p</i> -ethoxyPh.- 2- <i>p</i> -ethoxyPh-IT	Dark greyish brown	67	106-108°	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	12.24	12.17
5-Ph. azo-3-β-naphthyl- 2-β-naphthyl-IT	Greyish brown	70	170-72°	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ ON ₄ S	11.82	11.86
5- <i>p</i> -SulphonamidoPh.azo- 3- <i>p</i> -ethoxyPh.-2- <i>p</i> -ethoxy-Ph-IT	Deep yellow	60	128-29°	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₅ S ₂	13.05	12.98
5- <i>p</i> -SulphonamidoPh. azo- 3-β-naphthyl-2-β-naphthyl-IT	Reddish brown	75	175-77°	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	12.65	12.70

Ph. = phenyl; IT = iminothiazolid-4-one.

The 3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones were prepared according to the procedure of Markley and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2137) and Rao (*loc. cit.*) and the 5-arylazo derivatives were obtained by the method described earlier (Rao, *loc. cit.*; Bhargava *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

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